

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

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PRAGMATICITY OF RELIGIOUS TEXTS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

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